

Student Attitudes and the Level of Difficulties in Students' Spoken English at The Eldoret National Polytechnic, Kenya

Judith Nyamwaya^{1,2}, Robert Masinde², David Wanyonyi²

¹The Eldoret National Polytechnic, department of Business

²Moi University, department of Curriculum Instructions and Educational Media

*Corresponding author's Email: nyamwayajudith@gmail.com

Received Oct 2023; received in revised form 25th Jan 2024; accepted 13th Feb 2024

Abstract

The purpose of English language education is to provide students with the capabilities to use language in appropriate ways that demonstrate efficient mastery of spoken word. The study sought to determine the oral language difficulties experienced by students of Eldoret National Polytechnic pursuing different programmes at different levels. This study employed qualitative research paradigm as an intensive, holistic description, and analysis of a single instance, phenomenon. The study employed a descriptive method with multi instruments such as observation, questionnaires, and interviews. The population of this research comprised diploma level students in their final term of training. The result showed that students' behaviour indicated speaking difficulties. These difficulties in speaking was due to their problems with their motivation and self-confidence so that they feel quite hard to recognize their true skill. Somehow, many students have positive attitude and perception toward the concept of fluency in speaking English. They consider that fluency in speaking is something important to master; they think it will be very useful for their carrier in the future.

Keywords: Spoken English, Students Attitudes and Difficulties

Introduction

Students at tertiary level are expected to master English in both written and oral communication, because the aim of English language education is to provide students with the capabilities to understand the language and the ability to write and speak it (Richard, 2008).

A common phenomenon currently is, some students understand the English language very well but then experience difficulty and are uncomfortable when they have to speak. They are in doubt in their expressions yet they have to speak English in appropriate way to be understood. Richards and Renandya (2002) argue that the teaching and learning English should focus on both the forms of language and the functions of learning a language itself. In teaching oral communication, students should be immersed in the language. In view of the above, the study was conducted to establish the students' difficulties in speaking English and to know their attitude and perception toward speaking English as a foreign language in Eldoret Polytechnic.

Literature Review

According to Brown (2008) speaking skills and communication are closely intertwined and strengthen each other. The interaction of speaking as performance applies especially strongly to conversation. In the classroom, speaking is a skill that is most widely used for classroom interaction. In daily life, the skill of speaking is very useful to build a good or positive impression when meeting new people for the first time; it's also very good to build and maintain professional relationship at work.

The importance of communication in language learning can be so meaningful. Through reception we internalize linguistic information without which we could not produce language. "In classrooms, students always do more listening than speaking" (Brown, 2007).

The mastery of speaking skills in English is a priority for many foreign-language learners. Consequently, learners often evaluate their success in language learning as well as the effectiveness of their English course on the basis of how much they feel they have improved in their spoken language proficiency. Teachers and textbooks make use of a variety of approaches, ranging from direct approaches focusing on specific features of oral interaction (e.g., turn-taking, topic management, and questioning strategies) to indirect approaches that create conditions for oral interaction through group work, task work, and other strategies (Richards, 1990).

Subsequent pedagogical research on speaking skill made significant refinements in the process of speaking. Studies looked at the effect of a number of different contextual characteristics and

how they affect the speed and efficiency of processing oral communication. According to Rubin (1994) there are five factors of speaking process elements; the first factor is pronunciation, the second factor is interlocutor, the third factor is environment, and the fourth factor is confidence, while the last is process characteristics. Mental process also becomes important element process in the language and learning of speaking. As we know that a person who speaks foreign language for the first time needs so much effort and courage to do it confidently, especially when they are adult learners.

According to Richards (1990) ‘the conversation class is something of an enigma in language teaching’. It is clear that the goals and the techniques for teaching conversation are very diverse; it depends on the student, teacher, and overall context of the class. Pronunciation is also cannot be separated with the learning of speaking, even phonological details can be so meaningful in speaking English.

It is now very clear that fluency in speaking English and accuracy are both important goals to be achieved in communicative language teaching. While fluency, may we find if someone can master communicative language courses such as phonology, grammar, and discourse in their spoken output.

The affective factors can be one of the major obstacles to speak English fluently (Brown 2007). Because of the language ego that informs people that “you are what you speak”, so it makes students afraid of the judgment of the hearer. Very often, we can recognize whether someone is educated or uneducated from the way she or he speaks and the content of the speaking itself. The interaction effect is also very important in speaking, the hardest part is because the learners must recognize the multiplicity of sounds, words, phrase, and discourse forms that characterize any language, at the same time the learner must create interactive communication. In other words, one learners’ performance is always coloured by interlocutor he or she is talking with. In real life, we will be very glad if we can speak to an interactive interlocutor rather than the silent one.

Because speaking is two ways communication, where there must be at least a speaker and a listener, so that it can be a communicative dialogue.

The teaching of speaking in target language should enable the students to use the language orally for many purposes. The success of the teaching-learning process can be achieved if the teacher can present the materials in such a good way that can increase the students’ interest. The teacher should be creative in presenting English to the students. They also have to practice various techniques of teaching, carefully select the materials, and use interesting instructional

media that are suitable for the students in order to help them to speak in the language. Harmer (2001) states that there are many classroom speaking activities that can be used in teaching a language, such as acting from the script, communication games, discussion, prepared talks, as well as simulation and role play. In every classroom speaking activity, teacher must give students opportunity to speak what is in their mind, just like what is important and interesting for them to talk. It's better if teacher give students opportunity to express their understanding in English.

In English Foreign Language (EFL) classroom, the challenge may be happened in teaching and learning English. EFL students need more effort to learn listening and speaking because they don't live in a country which uses English as a main tool for communication. So, EFL students must search the way to be immersed in English in so many ways, participating in the classroom may be the appropriate way to practice speaking skill. In Indonesia, being an English student major means that the student must open his or her mind to media, such as printed media and electronic media which use English as the main language. So, it needs so much motivation and efforts.

Research Methodology

This study employed qualitative research design for a classroom setting. According to Alwasilah (2001), the classroom qualitative research has many advantages. The study was based on descriptive method.

The questionnaire had fifteen statements which covered the components of perceptions. The students' responses to items were recapitulated by using Likert scale and the data were then analysed and interpreted.

Research question number one and two are answered qualitatively. This research was conducted to find out students' difficulties when practicing speaking material used in their class, also to know about their perception about the concept of fluency of speaking English as a foreign language. Clearly, observational studies have been fundamental to this qualitative research. This study combined observation with interviewing, also questionnaire. This was because we had some research questions and because we wanted to use different methods or sources were to strengthen each other so that we used some form of methodological triangulation (Silverman, 2005).

Findings and Discussion

This study has showed a meaningful insight into the academic speaking practices of Eldoret Polytechnic students. It does not generalize these findings beyond the College but some significant findings are present in this study. In our findings, students' behaviour leads them to speaking difficulty, those who do not like speaking English activity, relatively get trouble in speaking for academic purposes. This study showed that students who experience difficulty with speaking often have problems with motivation and self-confidence. Individuals with speaking problems are more likely to attribute failure to a lack of personal ability and the things that make them hard to recognize their true skill. The connection between spoken difficulty and self-confidence were related specially with students' feeling, especially their role as speakers.

This study identified some characteristics that differentiate high achievers in oral language use from the low achievers. Both low achievers and high achievers attempted to speak English appropriately. Somehow, low achievers tended to focus on the meanings of single words. Low achievers tend to be less strategic. In fact, when given chance to start the communication, low achievers avoided starting a conversation. They failed to ask questions or request assistance to clarify difficulties. The Low achievers believed that the purpose of speaking was only to pronounce words correctly.

In contrast, high achievers used efficient strategies that relied more on processing in an interactive communication. They gave more attention and willingness to speak up their mind in classroom activities. Furthermore, high achievers concluded information accurately, clarified difficulties in appropriate way and predict what was likely to come next. They understood that making sense out of listening and speaking was important comprehending a whole context of conversation for successful interaction. In conclusion, high achievers were seen as very active and strategic listeners and speakers. They understand the purpose of listening and speaking in oral communication; they continuously paid attention to their comprehension, their fluency and bravely took corrective action when comprehension failure happened.

Many students have positive attitude and perception toward the concept of fluency of speaking English as a foreign language. They know about the importance of fluency in speaking English. Fluency in speaking English will be very useful for their career in future.

Conclusion

Teaching English in a world of change and challenge is a very complex process. Somehow, oral communication can be so interesting and important to learn. The result indicated that

students' behaviour toward speaking lead them to have difficulty in speaking for academic purposes. Subjects in low achievers spent less time in speaking activity and they pay a little attention to speaking activity in the classroom. However, subjects in high achievers spent more time in listening and speaking activity, high achievers always learn much more than low achievers. Somehow most of the students have a positive attitude and perception toward the concept of fluency in speaking English, they think that fluency in speaking English is something important to achieve for their academic life as a student and or their carrier as English teacher in the future. In conclusion, speaking English can be seen as a very essential life skill and activities which we use in academic life and in our daily life. Very often, we need to speak English clearly and understandable, so that the purpose of English education can be achieved. Students need to realize that speaking English is not only life style but also a necessity or requirement.

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